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***Spiribacter aquaticus* Leon et al. 2017 is a later heterotypic synonym of *Spiribacter roseus* Leon et al. 2016. Reclassification of *Halopeptonella vilamensis* Menes et al. 2016 as *Spiribacter vilamensis* comb. nov.**

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Running title: Reclassification of *Halopeptonella vilamensis* as *Spiribacter vilamensis* comb. nov.

Subject category: New taxa, Proteobacteria

Keywords: *Spiribacter*, *Halopeptonella*, taxonomy, synonym, halophilic bacteria

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The GenBank/EMBL/DDBJ accession numbers of the genomes are VMKP000000000 for *Spiribacter aquaticus* SP30^T and VMKO000000000 for *Halopeptonella vilamensis* DSM 21056^T, respectively.

26 **Abbreviations:** ANI, Average Nucleotide Identity; AAI, Average Aminoacids Identity;
27 BLAST, Basic Local Aligment Serach Tool, CECT, Colección Española de Cultivos
28 Tipo; DDH, DNA-DNA hybridization; DDBJ, DNA Data Bank of Japan; GGDC,
29 Genome-to-Genome Distance Calculator; IBRC, Iranian Biological Resources Center;
30 MEGA, Molecular Evolutionary Genetics Analysis; NCBI, National Center for
31 Biotechnology Information; PCR, Polymerase Chain Reaction; PG,
32 phosphatidylglycerol;
33

34 **Abstract**

35 A comparative taxonomic study of *Spiribacter* and *Halopeptonella* species was
36 carried out using a phylogenomic approach based on the comparison of the core
37 genome, Orthologous Average Nucleotide Identity (OrthoANIu), Genome-to-
38 Genome Distance Calculator (GGDC) and Average Amino Acids Identity (AAI).
39 The phylogenomic analysis based on 976 core translated gene sequences obtained
40 from their genomes showed that *Spiribacter aquaticus* SP30^T, *Spiribacter curvatus*
41 UAH-SP71^T, *Spiribacter roseus* SSL50^T, *Spiribacter salinus* M19-40^T and
42 *Halopeptonella vilamensis* DSM 21056^T formed a robust cluster, clearly separated
43 from the rest of species of closely related taxa. The AAI between *Halopeptonella*
44 *vilamensis* DSM 21056^T and the species of the genus *Spiribacter* was equal or greater
45 than 73.1%, confirming that all these species belong to the same single genus. On
46 the other hand, *Spiribacter roseus* SSL50^T and *Spiribacter aquaticus* SP30^T showed
47 percentages of OrthoANIu and digital DDH of 98.4 % and 85.3 %, respectively,
48 while these values among those strains and the type strains of the other species of
49 *Spiribacter* and *Halopeptonella vilamensis* DSM 21056^T were equal or lower than
50 80.8 % and 67.8 %, respectively. Overall, these data show that *Spiribacter roseus*
51 SSL50^T and *Spiribacter aquaticus* SP30^T constitute a single species and thus,
52 *Spiribacter aquaticus* SP30^T should be considered as a later, heterotypic synonym of
53 *Spiribacter roseus* SSL50^T based on the rules for priority of names. We propose an
54 emended description of *Spiribacter roseus*, including the features of *Spiribacter*
55 *aquaticus*. We also propose the reclassification of *Halopeptonella vilamensis* as
56 *Spiribacter vilamensis* comb. nov.

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58 The genus *Spiribacter* (family *Ectothiorhodospiraceae*, class *Gammaproteobacteria*)
59 was originally proposed in 2014 by León *et al.* [1,2]. Currently, this genus includes four
60 species: *Spiribacter salinus* [1,2] as the type species of the genus, *Spiribacter aquaticus*
61 [3], *Spiribacter curvatus* [4] and *Spiribacter roseus* [5] all of them isolated from Spanish
62 solar salterns [1-5]. The genus *Spiribacter* includes Gram-stain-negative, nonmotile and
63 curved-shaped cells. They are catalase and oxidase positive and moderately halophilic
64 bacteria, growing optimally at 10-15 % NaCl. The major cellular fatty acids are
65 C_{18:1ω6c}/C_{18:1ω7c}, C_{16:0}, and C_{10:0} 3-OH. The respiratory isoprenoid quinone is ubiquinone
66 Q8. The polar lipids are phosphatidylglycerol, phosphatidylethanolamine, a
67 phosphoglycolipid, a phosphoaminoglycolipid and three phospholipids. The DNA
68 content G+C content range is 60.0 to 66.0 mol% [1-5].

69 In 2016 a Gram-stain-negative, halophilic, heterotrophic, rod-shaped, non-endospore-
70 forming bacterium was isolated from the sediment of a hypersaline lake located in Laguna
71 Vilama, Argentina. The phylogenetic analysis based on 16S rRNA gene sequence and
72 phenotypic data suggested that this strain constituted a novel genus and species, for which
73 the name *Halopeptonella vilamensis* was proposed [6,7]. However, authors did not
74 consider the possibility of including the new taxa as a species of *Spiribacter*. In the
75 original description of *Halopeptonella vilamensis* only *Spiribacter salinus* was included
76 for comparison, even though *Spiribacter curvatus* was already described [6]. Besides, in
77 the description of *Spiribacter aquaticus*, *Halopeptonella vilamensis* was not included
78 since it was not published yet because these two species were described almost
79 simultaneously [3,6]. In order to compare all species of *Spiribacter* and *Halopeptonella*
80 *vilamensis*, we carried out a phylogenetic analysis based on 16S rRNA. The 16S rRNA
81 gene sequences of strains including in the analysis were obtained from the GenBank
82 database and the identification of phylogenetic neighbours and gene sequence similarity

83 were accomplished by EzBioCloud tool [8]. The 16S rRNA gene sequence was checked
84 against both primary and secondary structures of the 16S rRNA molecule using the
85 alignment tool of the ARB software package [9]. Phylogenetic trees were constructed
86 using three different methods, namely the maximum-likelihood [10], maximum-
87 parsimony [11], and neighbour-joining [12], algorithms integrated in the ARB software.
88 The analysis based on the comparison of 16S rRNA gene sequences revealed that
89 *Halopeptonella vilamensis* SV525^T is closely related to the four species of the genus
90 *Spiribacter*, showing similarities between 98.8 % to 95.6 %. Lower similarities were
91 obtained with respect to the other species analyzed. On the other hand, *S. roseus* and *S.*
92 *aquaticus* showed a 16S rRNA gene sequence similarity of 99.9 % between them.
93 Although this value is high, it is within the similarity values described among the species
94 of the genus *Spiribacter* [1-5]. The phylogenetic tree (Fig. 1) constructed by neighbour-
95 joining showed that *Halopeptonella vilamensis* SV525^T grouped with *Spiribacter* species,
96 and they constituted a single cluster (bootstrap value of 100 %) and thus, they could be
97 considered as members of the same genus. Similar tree topologies were obtained with
98 maximum-parsimony and maximum-likelihood algorithms (Fig. 1). Besides, in this 16S
99 rRNA phylogenetic tree, *S. roseus* SSL50^T and *S. aquaticus* SP30^T clustered together with
100 a bootstrap value of 100 %. In the description of *S. aquaticus* the DNA-DNA
101 hybridization studies were performed by the competition procedure of membrane filter
102 method. The DDH relatedness value between *S. roseus* SSL50^T and *S. aquaticus* SP30^T
103 was 55 %, a high value but lower than the 70 % threshold which is accepted for species
104 delineation [3,13, 14].
105 Until recently, the characterization and delineation of new species of prokaryotes was
106 based on a polyphasic approach carried out by the comparison of the 16S rRNA gene
107 sequence with the most closely related species, DNA-DNA hybridization and the

108 phenotypic characterization. Currently, genome sequencing is requested for the
109 description of a new prokaryotic species and the determination of genomic parameters
110 such as Average Nucleotide Identity (ANI), Average Amino Acids Identity (AAI) or
111 digital DNA-DNA (GGDC) hybridization are already mandatory for a complete analysis
112 of the new species [15].

113 Here, we have studied in detail the type strains of the four species of *Spiribacter* and the
114 single species of *Halotheonella* by comparison of their genomes. At the beginning of
115 this study only the genomes sequences of *S. salinus* M19-40^T (CP005963.1), *S. curvatus*
116 UAH-SP71^T (CP005990.1) and *S. roseus* SSL50^T (CP016382.1) were available. In order
117 to perform a comparative genomic study among all these species the draft genome
118 sequences of strains *S. aquaticus* SP30^T and *H. vilamensis* DSM 21056^T were determined.
119 The genomic DNA of both strains was extracted and purified using the Marmur method
120 [16]. Quality and concentration of DNA was determined by fluorometry (Qubic 3.0
121 Fluorometer, Thermofisher Scientific) and spectrophotometry (DeNovix DS-11 FX).
122 Draft genomes were sequenced using a whole-genome shotgun strategy with Illumina
123 HiSeq 4000 platform, using 150 bp paired-end sequencing reads (StabVida, Oeiras,
124 Portugal). The draft genomes of *S. aquaticus* SP30^T and *H. vilamensis* DSM 21056^T were
125 assembled in 32 and 4 contigs, respectively using Spades 3.9.1 [17]. The sequencing
126 depth were 211.2X and 238.2X coverage, respectively of the entire genomes, and the
127 resulting genomes assembly possessed N50 values of 454,578 and 804,265 bp,
128 respectively. Genome annotation was processed using the NCBI Prokaryotic Genomes
129 Automatic Annotation Pipeline and The Rapid Annotation using Subsystem Technology
130 (RAST) [18]. The genomes of *S. aquaticus* SP30^T and *H. vilamensis* DSM 21056^T were
131 estimated in 2,026,175 and 2,083,416 bp, with a G+C content of 65.6 and 64.1 mol%,

132 respectively. These values are in the range of the values described for the genus
133 *Spiribacter* (60-66 mol%) [1-5] (Supplementary Table S1).

134 We carried out a reconstruction of the phylogenomic core genome on the basis of the
135 comparison of the genomes of these species. All-versus-all BLAST search [19] was used
136 for comparisons of all translated protein-coding genes annotated from each available
137 genome. This analysis identified shared reciprocal best matches in all pairwise genome
138 comparisons (core orthologous genes) of strains of the genus *Spiribacter* and
139 *Halopeptonella* and the related taxa. MUSCLE [20] was used for the individual alignment
140 of the core orthologous genes with diagonal optimization and adjusting to 1 the maximum
141 number of iterations (default values for the other parameters). To create a core-genome
142 alignment, the resulting alignments were concatenated. A total of 976 single-copy
143 translated genes were shared by all strains (core orthologous). The phylogenomic tree
144 was reconstructed by the maximum-likelihood method based on the Tamura-Nei model
145 [21] using MEGA 7.0 software [22]. For the construction of this tree, we used the
146 sequences of the genomes of species of *Spiribacter*, *Halopeptonella* and other most
147 related species for which genomes were available in the databases. The phylogenomic
148 tree reconstruction (Fig. 2) revealed that the species of *Spiribacter* and *Halopeptonella*
149 *vilamensis* DSM 21056^T formed a single clade clustering in a different branch well
150 separated of the other species, confirming that all these five species belong to the same
151 genus, *Spiribacter*. Besides, this phylogenomic tree showed the close phylogenetic
152 relationship between *S. roseus* SSL50^T and *S. aquaticus* SP30^T.

153 For the analysis of genomes relatedness, the estimation of the average nucleotide identity,
154 the orthoANI values between the four described species of *Spiribacter* and *H. vilamensis*
155 DSM 21056^T were calculated. For the calculation of the orthologous gene percentages
156 (OrthoANIu), the OATsoftware from EZBioCloud server was used [23]. The OrthoANIu

157 showed percentages among *Halopeptonella vilamensis* DSM 21056^T and the species of
158 the genus *Spiribacter* between 73.3 to 83.7 % (Fig. 3) which were lower than the threshold
159 value for species discrimination (95-96 %) [15,24,25]. The OrthoANIu value between
160 *Spiribacter roseus* SSL50^T and *Spiribacter aquaticus* SP30^T was 98.4 %, which was
161 greater than the threshold value for species delineation, and shows that both species
162 belong to the same taxon (Fig. 3).

163 An alternative to ANI for more distantly related genomes is the average amino acid
164 identity (AAI). AAI between species of *Spiribacter* and *Halopeptonella* using CompareM
165 program [<https://github.com/dparks1134/CompareM>] was carried out. The AAI values
166 between *Halopeptonella vilamensis* DSM 21056^T and *Spiribacter aquaticus* SP30^T,
167 *Spiribacter curvatus* UAH-SP71^T, *Spiribacter roseus* SSL50^T and *Spiribacter salinus*
168 M19-40^T were 82.1, 87.1, 82.4 and 73.1 %, respectively. These values are above the
169 threshold considered for species of the same genus (60-70%) [26, 27].

170 In addition, in silico DNA-DNA hybridization (DDH) using the Genome-to-Genome
171 Distance Calculator (GGDC) website was performed [28]. Values were 56.3 % or lower
172 between *Halopeptonella vilamensis* DSM 21056^T and the species of the genus *Spiribacter*
173 (Fig. 3) proving that they are different taxa. The GGDC value between *Spiribacter roseus*
174 SSL50^T and *Spiribacter aquaticus* SP30^T was 85.3 % . Since the cut-off for this parameter
175 is well-established as 70 % for species delineation [15,28], these results give evidence that
176 *Spiribacter roseus* SSL50^T and *Spiribacter aquaticus* SP30^T constitute a single species.

177 In summary, the genome-based study shows that *S. roseus* and *S. aquaticus* constitute a
178 single species, having priority the name *S. roseus* according to the International Code of
179 Nomenclature of Prokaryotes [29]. And thus, *S. aquaticus* should be considered as a later
180 heterotypic synonym of *S. roseus*. We provide the emended description of *S. roseus*

181 including the features of *S. aquaticus*. On the other hand, we propose the reclassification
182 of *Halopectonella vilamensis* as *Spiribacter vilamensis* comb. nov.

183 Table 1 includes the differential characteristics of all these species.

184 **Emended description of *Spiribacter roseus* Leon et al. 2016**

185 *Spiribacter roseus* (ro'se.us. L. masc. adj. *roseus* pink pigmented).

186 The description is that of Leon et al. [5] with the following modification: colonies are
187 yellow-brown to pink pigmented, growth occurs at 7.5-25 % (w/v) NaCl, pH 7.0-9.0 and
188 15-40 °C. Optimum NaCl concentration, pH and temperature for growth are 10-12.5 %
189 (w/v), pH 7.5-8.0, and 37 °C.

190 The type strain is SSL50^T (= CECT 9117^T= IBRC-M 11076^T), isolated from the water of
191 a pond of Isla Cristina saltern, Huelva (Spain). The DNA G+C content of the type strain
192 is 64.2 mol% (determined by the T_m method) and 66.0 mol% (calculated from the
193 genome sequence).

194 The GenBank/EMBL/DDBJ accession numbers of the 16S rRNA gene sequence and
195 complete genome sequence of the type strain SSL50^T are LT578364 and CP016382.1,
196 respectively.

197 The species includes *Spiribacter aquaticus*, which is a heterotypic synonym of
198 *Spiribacter roseus*.

199

200 **Description of *Spiribacter vilamensis* comb. nov.**

201 *Spiribacter vilamensis* (vi.lam.en'sis. L. masc. adj. *vilamensis*, pertaining to Laguna
202 Vilama, Jujuy, Argentina).

203 Basonym: *Halopectonella vilamensis*

204 The description is the same as for *Halopectonella vilamensis* [6].

205 Type strain: SV525^T (= DSM 21056^T = JCM 16388^T= NCIMB 14596^T).

206 Source: Sediment of a hypersaline lagoon located at 4600 m above sea level
207 (Laguna Vilama, Argentina).
208 The GenBank/EMBL/DDBJ accession numbers of the 16S rRNA gene sequence and
209 complete genome sequence of *Halopeptonella vilamensis* DSM 21056^T are EU557314
210 and VMKO000000000, respectively.

211

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222

223 **Conflict of interest**

224 The authors declare that there are no conflicts of interest.

225

226 **Ethical statement**

227 No experimental work with animals or humans has been carried out in this study.

228

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309 **Table 1.** Differential characteristics of the species of the genus *Spiribacter* and *Halopeptonella vilamensis*.

	<i>S. salinus</i> M19-40 ^T	<i>S. curvatus</i> UAH-SP71 ^T	<i>S. roseus</i> SSL50 ^T	<i>S. aquaticus</i> SP30 ^T	<i>H. vilamensis</i> V525 ^T
Cells morphology	Curved to spiral	Curved rods, some short spiral cells	Curved rods to nearly closed rings, short spirals	Curved rods- nearly closed ring and spiral shapes	Rod
Colony pigmentation	Pink to dark pink	Pink	Pink	Yellow brown	Pink
pH range (optimum)	6.0-9.0 (7.5-8.0)	5.0-10.0 (8.0)	7.0-9.0 (7.5-8.0)	7.0-9.0 (8.0)	6.0-8.5 (7.0)
Temperature range (optimum) (°C)	15-40 (37)	5-40 (37)	15-40 (37)	20-40 (37)	10-35 (25-30)
NaCl concentration range (optimum) (% w/v)	10-25 (15)	5-20 (10)	8-20 (10)	7.5-25 (12.5)	7.5-25 (10-15)
Phosphatase	-	+	w	+	-
Urease	+	-	+	+	-
Fatty Acids	C _{18:1} ω6c and/or C _{18:1} ω7c, C _{16:0} and C _{10:0} 3-OH	C _{18:1} ω6c and/or C _{18:1} ω7c, C _{16:0} , C _{16:1} ω6c and/or C _{16:1} ω7c and C _{10:0} 3-OH	C _{18:1} ω6c and/or C _{18:1} ω7c, C _{16:0} and C _{12:0}	C _{16:0} , C _{18:1} ω7c, C _{19:0} cyclo ω8c and C _{12:0}	C _{18:1} ω7c, C _{16:0} , C _{18:0}
DNA G+C content (genome) (mol%)	62.7	63.9	66.0	65.4	60.4

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311 +: Positive; -: negative; w: weak

312 Data from: *Spiribacter salinus* [1]; *Spiribacter aquaticus* [3]; *Spiribacter curvatus* [4]; *Spiribacter roseus* [5]; *Halopeptonella vilamensis* [6].

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320 **Fig 1.** Neighbour-joining phylogenetic tree based on the comparison of 16S rRNA gene sequences showing the position of the species of the genus

321 *Spiribacter* and *Halopeptonella vilamensis* among other related species. Bootstrap values equal or higher than 70 % based on 1000 pseudoreplicates

322 are indicated at selected branch nodes. Filled circles indicate that the corresponding nodes were also obtained in the trees generated with the
323 maximum-parsimony and maximum-likelihood algorithms. *Methylothermus thermalis* MYHT^T (AY829009) was used as outgroup. Bar, 0.01
324 substitutions per nucleotide position.

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331 **Fig 2.** Phylogenomic tree based on the core orthologous genes of the type strain of the genus *Spiribacter* and *Halopeptonella vilamensis* and related
332 species, based on maximum-likelihood algorithm. This tree was obtained after the alignment of 976 shared orthologous single-copy translated
333 genes of these genomes. Bootstrap values higher than 70 % are indicated at branch-points. Bar, 0.05 substitutions per amino acid position.

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338 **Fig 3.** GGDC (lower triangle) and OrthoANIu (upper triangle) values for the type strains of the genus *Spiribacter* and *Halopeptonella vilamensis*.

339 Cells are filled with darker colors for higher values.

340